

An accurate and sample hybrid strategy for digital volume correlation

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Abstract: Digital volume correlation method (DVC) has been extensively employed to measure the three-dimensional deformation field of various materials. For the complexity of the algorithm, the computational efficiency of the DVC algorithm is hard to enhance. The existing incremental inverse-compositional Newton-Gauss algorithm (IC-GN) and curve-fitting algorithm exhibit larger computational efficiency, whereas they exhibit insufficient accuracy. Conventional IC-GN algorithm exhibits the high accuracy but low computational efficiency. Accordingly, to enhance the efficiency of the DVC algorithm, an accurate and simple hybrid strategy for DVC is developed in this study. First, the low-precision method is applied to assess the initial value of the displacement field and determine whether the calculation point exhibits a large deformation state. Subsequently, the high-efficiency incremental IC-GN algorithm is employed to assess the displacement continuously in the scenario of large strain; the curve-fitting method is exploited to assess the sub-voxel displacement under small strain. Lastly, the conventional IC-GN algorithm is employed to improve the sub-voxel accuracy based on the displacement assessed, and the time-consuming interpolation calculation should be merely calculated once, which is verified by numerical simulation experiments. As revealed from the results, after the curve-fitting algorithm is integrated with the conventional IC-GN algorithm, the calculation accuracy is significantly enhanced. The hybrid DVC method effectively maintains the accuracy of the conventional IC-GN algorithm, while fully exploiting the high efficiency of the curve-fitting algorithm and the incremental IC-GN algorithm. The speedup of the hybrid DVC method progressively increases from 0.8 to more than 2 with the increase in iterations.

Key words: Digital volume correlation; Hybrid strategy; IC-GN; Curve-fitting

1. Introduction

The Digital Volume Correlation Method (DVC) is extended by Bay et al. from the mature two-dimensional digital image correlation (DIC) technology [1]. Since 1999[2], the DVC method has been extensively employed to calculate and analyze the internal deformation characteristics of a wide variety of solid materials under external loading. The DVC technique refers to an effective tool to provide insights into the relationships between the macro-mechanical characteristic and micro-deformation of materials[3]; it also contributes to numerical simulation verification[4]. Over the past two decade, different researches have been committed to enhancing the accuracy and computing efficiency of DVC algorithms[5-9], and have developed a range of methods or strategies.

The IC-GN algorithm refers to an advanced matching algorithm[10], capable of accurately assessing large deformation displacements, and the hessian matrix requires calculation once only. However, while its iterative calculation remains time-consuming, and many studies on the optimization of DVC complied with the IC-GN method. During the iterative calculation of the IC-GN algorithm, interpolation calculation acts as an extremely time-consuming step. To enhance the interpolation efficiency, Pan et al.[6] used an interpolation coefficient lookup table. The interpolation coefficient lookup table should be merely calculated once, which considerably accelerates the calculation. Wang et al.[8] proposed a simple and effective incremental DVC method to simplify redundant interpolation calculations and reduce errors caused by interpolation calculations in IC-GN iterative calculations, which significantly enhances the computational efficiency of DVC algorithm under large strain. Recently, Wang et al.[9] adopted self-adaptive subvolume size to calculate the deformation of different regions in real materials; large strain area was calculated by small subvolume size, while small strain area was calculated by large subvolume size. Such method enhances the calculation accuracy while accelerating the calculation.

For small deformation scenarios, curve-fitting algorithm has also been employed to calculate the deformation field in the early studies. Compared with the IC-GN algorithm, the curve-fitting algorithm exhibits poor accuracy and stability,

and it can only be used for the small strain scenario, whereas the curve-fitting algorithm exhibits very high computational efficiency[11]. Recently, Li et al.[12] used the pre-interpolation method to considerably enhance the accuracy of the curve-fitting algorithm and maintained the efficiency of the algorithm. Li et al. also applied the pre-interpolation method in the incremental IC-GN algorithm, thereby enhancing the accuracy of the original incremental IC-GN algorithm. Compared with the conventional DVC algorithm, the maximum computational efficiency of DVC is up-regulated by approximately 8 times.

Over the past few years, as fueled by the rapid development of GPU hardware and software, GPU has been gradually employed in DVC algorithms, and the computing process has been significantly accelerated compared with CPU[13]. Moreover, the accuracy and computational efficiency of the algorithm still have much space for improvement. For instance, during the IC-GN iteration, though the interpolation coefficient lookup table method is applied, the interpolation calculation is also time-consuming; in the scenario of large deformation, the incremental IC-GN algorithm with higher computational efficiency may exhibit poor accuracy and system stability in some scenarios; though the pre-interpolation enhances the accuracy of the incremental algorithm, the pre-interpolation calculation takes up considerable memory, and the memory requirements increase by nearly 7 times, thereby reducing the applicability of the algorithm.

In this study, a simple hybrid strategy is applied in the DVC algorithm. First, the displacement field is assessed using a low-precision incremental DVC algorithm to determine whether it is a large deformation area. Second, for the large strain area, the incremental IC-GN algorithm is adopted to calculate the displacement field, while the small strain area is calculated using the curve-fitting method; lastly, to achieve more accurate calculation, the conventional IC-GN calculation is employed for calculation again based on the initial value of the displacement field, which requires interpolation calculation of the deformed volume image. The integer incremental IC-GN algorithm and curve-fitting algorithm exhibit high computational efficiency, whereas they have poor accuracy. Thus, the conventional IC-GN algorithm is adopted to remedy this defect. Furthermore, this strategy aims to legitimately draw upon the advantages of these methods and avoid defects.

2. Hybrid strategy for digital volume correlation

2.1 IC-GN--large strain

The interpolation calculation is very time-consuming in DVC calculation, seriously slowing down the calculation. Accordingly, Pan et al.[6] used interpolation coefficient lookup table to calculate sub-voxel interpolation, effectively simplifying redundant calculations, whereas this method requires considerable memory. Later, Wang et al.[8] used the incremental deformation method to deal with the interpolation problem, projecting the incremental position of each deformation to the nearest integer point position, and the simulation effect result suggested that the computational efficiency of the incremental IC-GN algorithm was further enhanced by approximately 2.5 times, while the error caused by interpolation calculation was reduced.

The basic principle of DVC algorithm is illustrated in Fig.1. According to the deformation function in continuum theory, the first-order deformation function is defined as:

$$\begin{cases} x' = x + u + u_x \Delta x + u_y \Delta y + u_z \Delta z \\ y' = y + v + v_x \Delta x + v_y \Delta y + v_z \Delta z \\ z' = z + w + w_x \Delta x + w_y \Delta y + w_z \Delta z \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where (x,y,z) denote the coordinates of the updated reference calculation point; $\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z$ are the local coordinates; u,v,w are three displacement components; $u_x, u_y, u_z, v_x, v_y, v_z, w_x, w_y, w_z$ represent nine displacement gradient parameters.

Fig. 1. Basic principle of DVC: matching the reference and target subvolumes.

The displacement iteration of the IC-GN algorithm is written as:

$$\mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p}) \leftarrow \mathbf{W}(\mathbf{W}^{-1}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p}), \mathbf{p}) = \mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p}) \cdot \mathbf{W}^{-1}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p}) \quad (2)$$

Where $\mathbf{p}=(u, u_x, u_y, u_z, v, v_x, v_y, v_z, w, w_x, w_y, w_z)$; $\Delta \mathbf{p}=(\Delta u, \Delta u_x, \Delta u_y, \Delta u_z, \Delta v, \Delta v_x, \Delta v_y, \Delta v_z, \Delta w, \Delta w_x, \Delta w_y, \Delta w_z)$; $\mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p})$ is the warp function; $\xi=(\Delta x, \Delta y, \Delta z)^T$ is the local coordinates of respective integer-voxel point.

$$\mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1+u_x & u_y & u_z & u \\ v_x & 1+v_y & v_z & v \\ w_x & w_y & 1+w_z & w \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x \\ \Delta y \\ \Delta z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{W}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p}) = \begin{bmatrix} 1+\Delta u_x & \Delta u_y & \Delta u_z & \Delta u \\ \Delta v_x & 1+\Delta v_y & \Delta v_z & \Delta v \\ \Delta w_x & \Delta w_y & 1+\Delta w_z & \Delta w \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \Delta x \\ \Delta y \\ \Delta z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The basic 3D IC-GN algorithm is illustrated in Fig.2. The IC-GN algorithm exploits the robust zero-mean normalized sum of squared difference (ZNSSD) to conduct matching analysis, as expressed in Eq.5, suggesting that the deformable subvolume should be constantly changed during the iteration, and the corresponding mathematical operation refers to interpolation calculation (for the specific process, please refer to [6]).

$$C_{ZNSSD}(\Delta \mathbf{p}) = \sum_{\xi} \left\{ \frac{f(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p})) - f_m}{\sqrt{\sum_{\xi} [f(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \Delta \mathbf{p})) - f_m]^2}} - \frac{g(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p})) - g_m}{\sqrt{\sum_{\xi} [g(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{W}(\xi; \mathbf{p})) - g_m]^2}} \right\}^2 \quad (5)$$

where $f(\mathbf{x})$ and $g(\mathbf{x})$ represent the gray values at point $\mathbf{x}=(x,y,z)^T$ in the reference and deformed subvolumes, respectively. f_m and g_m respectively denote the average gray level of reference and deformed subvolumes.

Fig. 2. Schematic illustration of the IC-GN algorithm[6].

Based on the conventional IC-GN algorithm, the incremental DVC method directly omits the interpolation calculation

step (Fig.3). On the whole, $\mathbf{p}$ or $\Delta\mathbf{p}$ are floating point values during the iteration, and the updated displacement coordinates (x,y,z) are also floating-point values. To acquire the deformed subvolume gray values at the centered point of (x, y, z) , interpolation calculation is required. However, the incremental IC-GN algorithm simplifies the interpolation calculation step, and its displacement iterative calculation equation is[8]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u(x, y, z) \\ v(x, y, z) \\ w(x, y, z) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} u(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) \\ v(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) \\ w(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} u_x(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) & u_y(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) & u_z(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) \\ v_x(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) & v_y(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) & v_z(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) \\ w_x(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) & w_y(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) & w_z(x_{\text{int}}, y_{\text{int}}, z_{\text{int}}) \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} (x - x_{\text{int}}) \\ (y - y_{\text{int}}) \\ (z - z_{\text{int}}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

where $x_{\text{int}} = \text{round}(x)$, $y_{\text{int}} = \text{round}(y)$, $z_{\text{int}} = \text{round}(z)$ denote the location of the nearest half-integer voxel of point (x,y,z) , defined as the center point of the offset reference subvolume.

The incremental IC-GN method exhibits high accuracy in displacement calculation in the scenario of large strain, whereas the algorithm is not optimistic for some sub-voxel displacement. When the sub-voxel displacement ranges from 0.4 voxel to 0.6 voxel, the error of the incremental IC-GN algorithm cannot be ignored. For instance, when subvolume size is $41 \times 41 \times 41$, the standard deviation ranges from 0.005 to 0.007 voxel, while the standard deviation of the conventional DVC algorithm ranges from 0.0006–0.0009 voxel. Though the computational efficiency of the incremental IC-GN algorithm is very high, the accuracy of the incremental algorithm is lower than that of the conventional IC-GN algorithm in some scenarios.

Fig. 3. Schematic of the nearest subvolume offset approach for incremental DVC[8].

2.2 Curve-fitting -- small strain

In the real DVC analysis, the measuring error may be difficult to control if the strain is too large, so the deformation difference between two adjacent times is generally not large. On the whole, the average strain value of the material is small after deformation (e.g., the strain less than 5%), while the local strain may be large (e.g., the shear strain probably exceeding 20% of shear band). Though in the iteration of the incremental IC-GN algorithm, though the hessian matrix requires calculation once only, the calculations of multiplication and inversion of the remaining matrices remain very large. As a result, it is more time-consuming to use incremental IC-GN method to calculate small strain. Pan et al.[11] had compared the subpixel accuracy and stability of curve-fitting method, gradient method and Newton method; it was suggested that Newton method exhibits the optimal calculation accuracy and stability, followed by gradient method; curve-fitting method is the worst, with the accuracy not satisfying the calculation requirements. However, the calculation speed of the curve-fitting algorithm is nearly 27 times than that of Newton algorithm for DIC algorithm[11, 14], and the difference between of them may be larger in DVC calculation. Thus, it is more suitable to assess the displacement using the curve-fitting method under small strain.

First, an integer search algorithm is employed to find the position of the integer point of the extreme value of the zero-mean normalized cross correlation (ZNCC). To find the overall voxel position with the maximal similarity, and obtain the integer voxel displacement of the measured point, the integer voxel displacement search algorithm adopts a correlation function to search point by point in a specified range of the deformed volume image [2]. To enhance the

computational efficiency, the integer voxel search strategy can use optimized search methods (e.g., thickness search method[15], extended search method[16], and global summation table method based on recursive strategy[17]). Furthermore, integer voxel displacement search can also be conducted in the frequency domain, and three-dimensional fast Fourier transform[18, 19] can carry out efficient frequency domain matching calculations.

Subsequently, the ZNCC equation is established at the extreme point, set the ZNCC equation be $C(x,y,z)$, and the general curve-fitting equation refers to a ternary quadratic function[20]:

$$C(x, y, z) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2y + a_3z + a_4xy + a_5xz + a_6yz + a_7x^2 + a_8y^2 + a_9z^2 \quad (7)$$

In some studies, the least square method was employed to solve the parameters of Eq.7[11], whereas the least square method involves some complicated matrix operations; the calculation is time-consuming, and the calculation accuracy is not sufficiently high. Accordingly, the display calculation method is referenced to assess the sub-voxel displacement[12].

2.3 Improve calculation accuracy

Different strain regions adopt different calculation methods to assess the initial value of the displacement field. Compared with the conventional DVC algorithm, the curve-fitting algorithm exhibits a computational efficiency up to 7-8 times, and the incremental IC-GN algorithm can reach 2.5 times. Thus, the small strain area is assessed by a low-precision curve-fitting algorithm, and the large strain area is assessed by a higher-precision incremental IC-GN algorithm. Though these two algorithms exhibit high computational efficiency, their accuracy is relatively poor. It is generally known that the conventional IC-GN algorithm exhibits high accuracy and excellent algorithm stability[11]. To fully exploit the merits of different algorithms and try to avoid their disadvantages, based on the initial values assessed by these integer algorithms, the conventional IC-GN algorithm is employed to achieve more accurate calculation in the last step.

Fig.4 schematically illustrates the strategy flow of the hybrid DVC algorithm, and there is not interpolation calculation in the calculations of the curve-fitting method and the incremental IC-GN method. The specific implementation steps of the strategy include:

- Step 1: Using a relative large subvolume (e.g., $41 \times 41 \times 41$) to assess the entire displacement field of some vital points, and subsequently assess the initial value of the entire displacement field, and determine whether these measurement points are in a large deformation state.
- Step 2: Based on the initial value of the displacement field, the curve-fitting algorithm is adopted to further assess the small deformation area to enhance the accuracy of the displacement estimation.
- Step 3: In the large deformation area, the incremental IC-GN algorithm is employed to assess the displacement field. The hessian matrix and other intermediate variables calculated in the incremental IC-GN algorithm steps can be used again.
- Step 4: Based on the more accurate initial values assessed using the curve-fitting method and the incremental IC-GN method, the conventional IC-GN calculations are used again to calculate the displacement field to enhance accuracy. Furthermore, the spline method is selected for the interpolation.

The hybrid DVC method strategy could fully draw upon the high efficiency of the incremental IC-GN algorithm and the curve-fitting algorithm and the high accuracy of the conventional IC-GN algorithm, while enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of the DVC algorithm; it also avoids time-consuming interpolation calculations.

Fig. 4. Flowchart showing the hybrid DVC strategy.

3. Experimental verification using numerical tests

3.1 Accuracy of hybrid DVC method

In this study, the random speckle generation method is employed to generate a volume image with a size of $200 \times 200 \times 200$ voxels ($s=96,000$, $R=4$ voxels), as presented in Fig.5a. Subsequently, complying with Fourier's displacement method[21], 10 volume images with sub-voxel displacements in the z direction from 0.1 to 1 voxel and interval of 0.1 voxel are generated. Lastly, a random Gaussian noise with a mean value of 0 and a variance of 4 is added to those volume images to simulate the effect of noise. All DVC calculations comply with the MATLAB 2018b platform, the computer configuration parameters include Inter Core i7-6700 CPU 3.40 GHz and memory 8GB RAM, while the mixed programming technology of C/C++ or Fortran is not used.

Fig.5 shows the sub-voxel calculation accuracy of the incremental IC-GN algorithm and curve-fitting method with different subvolumes. Figs.5a-b indicate that when the sub-voxel displacement falls in a certain range, the accuracy of the incremental IC-GN algorithm decreases considerably, far from that of the conventional IC-GN algorithm. Among them, the mean bias error of the incremental IC-GN algorithm is similar to that of the conventional IC-GN, whereas the standard deviation of the sub-voxel displacement increases. Note that when the sub-voxel displacement ranges from 0.4 voxel to 0.6 voxel, the standard deviation value of the incremental IC-GN algorithm rises rapidly.

Fig.5c-d present the sub-voxel calculation accuracy of the curve-fitting algorithm. These figures reveal the mean bias error of the curve-fitting algorithm similar to that of the incremental IC-GN algorithm, while the standard deviation of the displacement is worse than that of the incremental IC-GN algorithm. The standard deviation curves display large fluctuations, 2-3 times larger than that of the incremental IC-GN algorithm. In brief, the accuracy of curve-fitting algorithm and the incremental IC-GN algorithm cannot satisfy the requirements of calculation without pre-interpolation processing[12].

Fig. 5. Measure z displacements as a function of sub-voxel displacement assessed with different subvolume size of Incremental IC-GN algorithm and curve-fitting algorithm: (a) and (c) mean bias error, (b) and (d) standard deviation error. (incremental IC-GN as IC-GN int)

Fig.6 gives the sub-voxel calculation accuracy of the hybrid curve-fitting algorithm and the conventional IC-GN algorithm, the hybrid incremental IC-GN algorithm, as well as the conventional IC-GN algorithm. The figure reveals that regardless of the initial value of the displacement field based on the curve-fitting algorithm or the incremental IC-GN algorithm, the sub-voxel mean bias error and standard deviation are noticeably improved after the conventional IC-GN algorithm is applied. The curves of the two methods in Fig.6 show similar trends, the curve values are small, and the changes are stable.

To compare the accuracy and stability of different algorithms, the subvolume size is set to $41 \times 41 \times 41$. Fig.7 draws the comparison of sub-voxel displacement accuracy curves of curve-fitting algorithm, incremental IC-GN algorithm, as well as its hybrid DVC algorithm. The comparison indicates that compared with the incremental IC-GN algorithm, the accuracy of the hybrid algorithm is significantly enhanced, the mean bias error is reduced by nearly 60% to 80%, and the standard deviation is reduced by 40% to 60%. Compared with the curve-fitting algorithm, the mean bias error of the hybrid algorithm is reduced by nearly 60% to 70%, and the standard deviation is reduced by 70% to 80%. In brief, the accuracy of the existing curve-fitting algorithm and incremental IC-GN algorithm is worse than that of conventional IC-GN algorithm, while the proposed hybrid algorithm is capable of maintaining the high accuracy of conventional IC-GN algorithm.

Fig. 6. Measure z displacements as a function of sub-voxel displacement assessed and different subvolume size of hybrid DVC methods: (a) and (c) mean bias error, (b) and (d) standard deviation error.

Fig. 7. Measure z displacements as a function of sub-voxel displacement assessed: (a) mean bias error and (b) standard deviation error.

3.2 Computational efficiency of hybrid DVC method

In the previous section, the accuracy results of the hybrid DVC algorithm are compared with the curve-fitting algorithm and the incremental IC-GN algorithm. As revealed from the results, the hybrid DVC algorithm maintains the high-accuracy characteristics of the conventional IC-GN algorithm. The hybrid DVC algorithm has the accuracy of the conventional IC-GN algorithm, and its computational efficiency is also a critical issue. In this section, the computational efficiency of the hybrid DVC algorithm is discussed.

Fig.8 show the computational efficiency of the hybrid DVC algorithm and the conventional IC-GN algorithm, which can be summarized into two categories:

1) Under small strain, the initial value of the displacement field is first assessed by the curve-fitting algorithm, and subsequently the accuracy is improved by the conventional IC-GN algorithm. Since the curve-fitting algorithm exhibits

very high computational efficiency, the time consumed in the initial value estimation of the displacement field is relatively short. In the conventional IC-GN algorithm calculation, though it should be merely calculated once, it must calculate some intermediate calculation variables (e.g., hessian matrix). As a result, the calculation speed of the hybrid DVC algorithm is approximately 3 times than that of the conventional IC-GN algorithm.

2) under large strain, the conventional IC-GN algorithm directly maintains the intermediate variables and parameter results of the incremental IC-GN algorithm in the calculation, avoiding the time of repeated calculations. The computational efficiency of the incremental IC-GN algorithm is 2.5 times than that of the conventional IC-GN algorithm[8], however the conventional IC-GN algorithm at the last step is relatively time-consuming, especially the calculation steps related to the interpolation calculation. The computational efficiency of the hybrid DVC algorithm is nearly 1.25 times than that of the conventional IC-GN algorithm. The question arises that why the speedup of the hybrid DVC algorithm is only 1.25 times. This is because in the existing numerical simulation calculation, the number of iterations of the incremental IC-GN algorithm is only approximately 2, so the computational efficiency is slightly enhanced.

Fig. 8. Experimental computing speed of the hybrid DVC methods to the traditional DVC method.

In the calculation of deformation of real materials, for the small strain of the material, the curve-fitting algorithm can be calculated efficiently, while the number of iterations of the incremental IC-GN algorithm may be less than three. However, for the relatively large and complex strain of the real material, the number of iterations of the incremental IC-GN algorithm or the conventional IC-GN algorithm will increase, for instance, the number of iterations may exceed 5 times. Fig.9 shows the speedup of the hybrid IC-GN algorithm with different iterations. At the number of iterations as 1, the acceleration ratio is only nearly 0.8. This is because the conventional IC-GN algorithm calculation is added after the incremental IC-GN algorithm calculation, so the computational efficiency of hybrid IC-GN algorithm is lower than that of the conventional IC-GN algorithm, However, this special case is rare during the calculation of strain fields in real materials. As the increasing of iterations, the advantages of the hybrid IC-GN algorithm are progressively enhance, and the acceleration ratio tends to increase. Comparing the conventional IC-GN algorithm, the computational efficiency of incremental IC-GN algorithm could increase 2.5 times, so the upper limit of the acceleration ratio of hybrid IC-GN algorithm is approximately 2.5. (For different programming skills and implementation platforms, some differences may exist in these calculation results)

Those incremental IC-GN algorithm and curve-fitting algorithm can be generalized, termed as integer method, the conventional IC-GN method can be named floating-point calculation method, and the most significant characteristic of integer calculation method is that it does not need interpolation calculation. In the hybrid DVC method, the initial value of any displacement is assessed using the integer methods, while the high-precision displacement calculation uses the floating-point method. As in the conventional IC-GN algorithm iteration, the interpolation calculation is a very time-

consuming step. Though Pan et al.[6] used the interpolation coefficient table lookup table method to solve this problem well, the improved interpolation calculation remains time consuming. In the calculation of the hybrid DVC algorithm, the time-consuming interpolation calculation requires calculation once only, as a result, the hybrid DVC algorithm could significantly enhance the computational efficiency of the conventional DVC algorithm. The hybrid DVC method and its strategy not only fully draw upon the advantages of the high computation speed of the curve-fitting algorithm and the incremental IC-GN algorithm in the initial estimation of the displacement field, but also maintains the high-precision characteristics of the conventional IC-GN algorithm.

Fig. 9. Comparison the computer speed ratio of hybrid DVC strategy and traditional DVC method along with the iteration number.

4 Conclusion

Various factors can restrict the accuracy and computational efficiency of the existing DVC algorithms. The curve-fitting algorithm and incremental DVC algorithm exhibit higher computational efficiency, while the sub-voxel displacement accuracy is relatively poor; the conventional IC-GN algorithm exhibits high accuracy and stability, whereas the interpolation calculation is highly time-consuming in the IC-GN algorithm iteration. The proposed hybrid DVC method first exploits the efficient curve-fitting algorithm and the incremental DVC algorithm to assess the initial value of the displacement field, and subsequently uses the conventional IC-GN algorithm to achieve more accurate calculation. The hybrid DVC algorithm strategy could fully draw upon the high efficiency of the first two algorithms, while using the conventional IC-GN algorithm to make up for the shortcomings of precision complementation. During the calculation of the hybrid DVC method, the conventional IC-GN algorithm should be merely calculated once. Accordingly, as the increasing of iterations of the incremental IC-GN algorithm, the acceleration ratio of the hybrid DVC method will be more significant. The theoretical acceleration ratio progressively is up-regulated from 0.8 to the limit of 2.5.

Compared with the existing DVC algorithm, though the hybrid DVC algorithm has higher accuracy and acceleration ratio, how to effectively determine whether the calculation point exhibits a large or small strain state, and how to effectively combine with the curve fitting algorithm and IC-GN Algorithms are the focus of subsequent study.

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